

DEVELOPING SPEAKING SKILLS IN MIXED CLASSES

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the importance of communication skills, especially speaking skills of English, in all spheres of life. Moreover, the benefits or advantages of speaking skills in grabbing the opportunities in global market are discussed comprehensively. This article emphasizes the role of a teacher in enhancing learners' speaking skills by applying various methods, techniques and approaches in English language classrooms.

At the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, deep reforms are being carried out in the education system. One such reform is aimed at improving language learning and spoken culture. The correct formulation of speech is regulated at all stages of human learning.

Type of speech is the use of language-based thinking. Speech functions as a function of communication and communication, emotional expression and influence on others. Well-developed speech is one of the most important tools for a person's active participation in society, and to develop students' speech, teachers need to use methods and techniques that help them master their pronunciation, vocabulary, syntactic structure and connected speech.

Currently, much attention of specialists in the field of teaching foreign languages is focused on how to develop and improve speaking skills in a foreign language. Teachers of linguistic universities, financial and economic, pedagogical, as well as many other non-linguistic universities address this problem. This need arises due to the fact that, due to long-standing traditions, the practice of cooperation between English and foreign companies has been maintained; in addition, the development of tourism leads to the formation of the habit of planning trips and trips to foreign countries where the possibility of communicating in a foreign language is quite high.

Once in the country of the language they are learning, people tend to feel more fully involved in the process of communication in a variety of subject areas and at different levels of complexity. Thus, students sitting in university classrooms, or adults hunched over the keyboards of their computers in offices, again and again return to the question of how to master the science of communication in a foreign language faster, more productively and more fun.

Students of foreign language groups cannot speak clearly and freely without sufficient vocabulary. Each new word increases their vocabulary, increasing their ability to express

themselves. This is why it is necessary to constantly work with students so that they master the words and their meanings. In this case, it is important to include synonyms and antonyms in their speech on a regular basis. The teacher must remember that words are a necessary element of the text.

The term “blended learning” began to be widely used in teaching methods after the publication of the book “Handbook of Blended Learning” by Bonk and Graham in 2006, in which blended learning is defined as a system of harmonious interaction between face-to-face and distance learning processes¹.

There are different definitions of blended learning. Thus, Horn and Staker define blended learning as formal educational programs in which students are taught at least partially in an electronic, online format, and at the same time there are some elements of control over the timing, flow and pace of learning; some of the training takes place face-to-face². Such training uses different models to ultimately provide an integrated learning experience. Bonk and Graham understands blended learning as the integration of electronic and traditional learning, which is characterized by consistency and pedagogical value. Approximately the same definition is given in blended learning is a form of learning in which training is carried out both in traditional face-to-face form and using distance learning technologies³. The following definition seems to be the most capacious and laconic. Blended learning is a model built on the basis of the integration and mutual complementarity of traditional and e-learning technologies, which involves replacing part of traditional training sessions with various types of educational interaction in the electronic environment.

The percentage of blended learning components depends on various factors: the age and preparation of students, subject of study, qualifications and competence of the teacher, etc. Typically, e-learning makes up from 30 to 79% of teaching time.

With blended learning, the teacher still remains at the center of the educational process, but with the help of new methods and technological tools, he makes the educational process more interesting and effective. Here the teacher acts as a consultant who helps students analyze emerging problems and find ways to solve them. On the other hand, this form of education is very useful for students, because conditions are created for active student activity, the habit of self-learning is stimulated, information search skills appear, the ability for continuous education is formed, intellectual abilities are expanded, etc.⁴.

The blended learning method was first introduced in American higher education institutions, and later in schools. Thus, in 2009, blended learning technologies were available to three million American schoolchildren, and by 2019, it is planned to conduct about 50% of all lessons using online methods⁵.

¹ Bonk C.J., Graham C.R. The Handbook of Blended Learning. Global Perspectives, Local Designs. Hardcover – December 30, 2005. URL: <http://www.google.lv/books?id=2u2TxK06PwUC&printsec=frontcover#v=onepage&q&f=false> (дата обращения: 19.01.2015).

² Friesen N. Report: Defining Blended Learning. URL: <http://www.learningspace.org/>

³ Кравцов В.В., Савельева Н.Н., Черных Т.В. Смешанное обучение как ответ на вызовы современному образованию // Образовательные технологии и общество. – 2015. – Т. 18, №4. – С. 659-669. URL: <http://ifets.ieee.org/russian/periodical/journal.html>

⁴ Allen E., Seaman J., Garrett R. Blending In: The Extent and Promise of Blended Education in the United States. – I. Sloan-C™, 2007. – 35 p.

⁵ Horn, M.B., Staker H. The Rise of K–12 Blended learning. URL: <http://www.christenseninstitute.org/wp-content/uploads/2013/04/The-rise-of-K-12-blended-learning.pdf>

In schools in other countries, the process of introducing blended learning is not as active. However, an analysis of studies indicates that the methodological foundations of this technology and the methodological plan for its use are insufficiently studied.

The problem of speech development in foreign language groups should always be in the spotlight. Working with DRM (didactic handouts), using ICT (information and communication technologies), organizing didactic games helps develop oral and written speech. First of all, it should be noted that didactic games are suitable for student speech. A fun game is desirable and enjoyable for people of any age. Thanks to these technologies, students are motivated to attend classes. Speech development becomes a prerequisite for professional and personal development. Therefore, the problem of oral speech development is always in the spotlight.

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